

Task Collection Adjustments & Decisions

This appendix contains the decisions for the first adjustment of the task collection (based on the survey results) and the decisions for the second adjustment of the task collection (based on the interview results).

1.1 First adjustment of the tasks and mapping for variables

Task ID	Decision	Reasoning
V1C1	keep	The suggestion from P9 to reformulate the related errors does not imply that the related errors and MC can't be mapped to and therefore be expected from the tasks. We - and the two other participants - think that the formulation is appropriate.
V2C1	keep	Again P9 suggested to rephrase the related errors, but at the same time P9 also expressed their full agreement for the mapping of the errors.
V3C1	keep	Full agreement
V4C1	keep	Full agreement
V5C1	keep	Full agreement
V6C1	keep	We don't agree with the comment that the correct answer and the expected error contradict each other. Furthermore, novices who would solve the tasks would not see the description of the correct answer and the expected error.
V7C1	keep	See above
V1C2	adjust	Based on the feedback from the participants, the task was rephrased to contain more specific instructions.
V2C2	adjust	We rephrased the task based on the feedback from P7 and P8 and mentioned that neither the first line, nor the second line of the code could be changed. Thus we can avoid novices to give the function an argument.
V3C2	adjust	To avoid students removing the print statement, we rephrased the instructions for the task accordingly.
V1C3	keep	Full agreement

1.2 Second adjustment of the tasks and mapping for variables

Task ID	Decision	Reasoning
V1C1	keep	Tasks assess different concepts
V2C1	keep	
V3C1	keep	
V4C1	keep	
V5C1	keep	
V6C1	remove	We removed tasks V6C1 and V7C1 as the related errors, e.g. value assignment in the wrong direction would be caught by a compiler and count as 'syntax' errors that can be neglected according to the findings from our interview.
V7C1	remove	
V1C2	keep	Kept with the adjustments proposed in 2.1
V2C2	keep	
V3C2	keep	
V1C3	adjust	We removed the additional 'restriction' of not setting end to a specific value, as this restriction does not help to assess or show whether students understand the concept of writing a loop that sums up values.

2.1 First adjustment of the tasks and mapping for loops

Task ID	Decision	Reasoning
L1C1	keep	Full agreement
L2C1	keep	Even if one participant disagreed on the appropriateness of the difficulty level, we could not comprehend their reasoning. In addition, one participant suggested to edit the task description slightly to stress the printing and not only the looping. We don't believe that this is necessary as the task is a fill-the-gap task and the printing is already included in the code and can't be edited.
L3C1	adjust	Two participants disagreed on the appropriateness and commented that there is more than one solution to this task. They are right and therefore we considered the suggestion and moved L3C1 from class 1 to class 2.
L4C1	keep	Even if one participant stated that the while else construct is tied to Python and we agree that an else block in connection with a while loop is unusual in most programming languages, we think that this possibility could be mentioned when introducing while loops to novices and decided to keep the task as a 'bonus task' .
L5C1	adjust	Even if all participants totally agreed with the appropriateness of the class and the suitability of the error, we followed up on the comment of one participant and removed the prompt ("Use a comma to separate a new line").
L1C2	keep	Full agreement
L2C2	keep	
L3C2	keep	
L4C2	keep	Even if one participant did not agree with the mapping of the errors, the participant did not provide a reason. Therefore, we decided to keep the task as is.
L5C2	keep	Even if one participant disagreed on the mapping for the difficulty and found the task too easy for level 2, two other participants agreed, and we also think that the task is appropriate and is not too easy.
L2C3	keep	Full agreement

2.2 Second adjustment of the tasks and mapping for loops

Task ID	Decision	Reasoning
L1C1	adjust	We kept the gap for the while statement but removed the gap for the ":"
L2C1	adjust	We kept the gap for the "for" and "in" statement but removed the gap for the ":"
L3C1	adjust	Using the 'break' statement wouldn't necessarily mean that students know what it does and understand the concept behind it. Instead, we designed a new task that uses a flowchart to assess the understanding of 'break'
L4C1	adjust	Similar to the reasoning for L3C1, we created a new task that uses a flowchart to assess the understanding of the 'else'.
L5C1	keep	Kept with the adjustments proposed in 3.1
L1C2	keep	Tasks assess different concepts
L2C2	keep	
L3C2	keep	
L4C2	keep	
L5C2	keep	
L2C3	adjust	We removed the additional 'restriction' of not defining the range, as this restriction does not help to assess or show whether students understand the concept of testing for prime numbers or not.

3.1 First adjustment of the tasks and mapping for functions

Task ID	Decision	Reasoning
F1C1	adjust	We followed up on the participant's comment and rephrased the task to make it explicit that we are asking for a function that requires no input.
F2C1	keep	Full agreement
F3C1	remove	One participant stated that the task was very trivial and we agree with this comment. As we have other tasks that are related to the understanding of parameters (such as F3C2 or F5C2), we removed this task from our task collection.
F4C1	keep	The criticism for multiple solutions for this task would apply, if the task required input in a free text field. However, the way the task and the gaps are currently formulated, only one solution is possible.
F1C2	adjust	The task was rephrased due to the comment of the participant who disagreed on mapping of the errors. We ensured that the function respects and uses the given arguments and additionally changed the name of the function to better match its functionality in the program as suggested by the participant.
F2C2	keep	Despite of the comments, we kept the task as is. Nevertheless, we will remember the comment that this type of nesting is rarely used in practice (and consider F2C2 as a bonus task instead of a prioritized task for our task collection).
F3C2	keep	Full agreement
F4C2	keep	Even if one participant criticized that the task was too easy for class 2, the two other participants and we agree to the mapping of the difficulty
F5C2	keep	One participant stated that the task was not well formulated, and the task was not clear. Hence, we adjusted the phrasing of the task.
F1C3	adjust	The task was rephrased based on the participant's comment of using 'arguments' and not 'variables' as the appropriate wording when we are talking about functions.
F2C3	adjust	The task was adjusted to include the information whether the data type must be queried in advance and how to handle the case if all numbers were identical.

3.2 Second adjustment of the tasks and mapping for functions

Task ID	Decision	Reasoning
F1C1	adjust	We combined tasks F1C1 and F2C1 into one task with two gaps to (1) define a function and (2) call the function.
F2C1	adjust	
F4C1	adjust	To assess the conceptual understanding of the return statement, we adjusted this tasks and created two subtasks: One subtask includes a return statement whereas the other does not include a return statement. We will ask the user what each function would return.
F1C2	keep	Kept with the adjustments proposed in 4.1
F2C2	keep	As mentioned in 4.1 we considered this task as a bonus task instead of a prioritized task for our task collection.
F3C2	keep	Tasks assess different concepts
F4C2	keep	
F5C2	keep	
F1C3	adjust	Kept with the adjustments proposed in 4.1
F2C3	adjust	